

Modified Ying-Yang Flap for a Problematic Lesion in the Back Region

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Abstract

The Ying-Yang flap has been established as a safe and reliable option for the reconstruction of defects of varying sizes, providing effective tension distribution across multiple vectors while remaining less invasive than many conventional techniques. The evenly distributed tension promotes fast wound healing, preserves the anatomical integrity of surrounding tissues, and often results in a well-camouflaged final result. However, the technique can be further modified to achieve a more personalized reconstructive approach.

In our case, a modified Ying-Yang was utilized for the reconstruction of a circular defect of the back following surgical excision of a problematic lesion. This modification offered several key advantages: 1) balanced tension distribution across multiple vectors, 2) preservation of native tissue architecture, 3) maintenance of vascular integrity to support flap viability, and 4) avoidance of complications commonly associated with skin grafts or more invasive reconstructive options - thereby providing a safer and functionally superior outcome.

Introduction

Innovative thinking drives progress - a mindset that should be embedded in every dermatologic and reconstructive surgeon. Innovation has always been fundamental to plastic and reconstructive surgery, serving as the foundation for techniques that are simpler, more effective, less invasive, and less morbid, while achieving functional and aesthetic outcomes [1]. Classical reconstructive techniques, when refined through subtle modifications, can theoretically achieve superior surgical outcomes by ensuring a functionally balanced defect closure, optimizing tension distribution across multiple vectors, and maintaining both anatomical integrity and functional preservation [2].

Resection of medium- or large-sized defects may result in substantial skin loss, often making skin grafting the first-line reconstructive option [3]. However, due to poor cosmetic outcomes - such as visible color and texture mismatch - or partial graft failure, this approach is often less desirable [3]. In such cases, tissue rearrangement techniques, primarily local skin flaps, offer superior functional and cosmetic results [3].

Case Report

We present here the case of a 68-year-old male with a problematic lesion on the vertebral region of the back, clinically suspected to be chronic epidermal cyst (Figure 1). Due to the chronic nature of the lesion, and the patient's request for removal, surgical excision was

More Information

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performed under local anesthesia with 2% lidocaine diluted in normal saline and a few drops of adrenaline.

Figure 1: Preoperative View: A Formation Located on the Back, Solid to Touch, Clinically Suspected for Epidermal Cyst

The excision resulted in a medium-sized circular defect. Considering the limited skin mobility, cutaneous thickness, and underlying tension vectors in this anatomical area, reconstruction was planned using the Ying-Yang flap.

The Ying-Yang flap is a double opposing rotational flap that can be safely applied to less conventional anatomical regions (Figure 1). It is particularly suitable for the reconstruction of circular defects in areas with limited skin mobility, as it effectively redistributes tension across multiple vectors.

To minimize distortion of the adjacent skin, the rotational flaps were designed in a ying and yang manner, with each flap measuring approximately twice the diameter of the primary defect. The curvilinear incision begins at the superolateral or inferolateral margin of the defect, followed by careful flap elevation (Figure 2), dissection and undermining down to the hypodermis to preserve the subcutaneous pedicle and maintain adequate vascular supply. The resulting closure forms an S-shaped configuration resembling a shuriken (Figure 3).

Figure 2: Intraoperative View: Flap Dissection and Undermining Down to the Hypodermis to Preserve the Subcutaneous Pedicle and Maintain Adequate Vascular Supply

Figure 3: Intraoperative View: the Secondary Wound Defect Forming an S-Shaped Configuration, Resembling a Shuriken

During intraoperative adaptation, tension was noted at the inferior margin of the lower opposing flap. To achieve proper alignment and ensure tension-free closure, an additional small relieving equilateral triangle was made at this site, with its base toward the inferior opposing flap and the two sides directed inferiorly. The triangle was subsequently removed. This additional modification led to the creation of a modified Ying-Yang flap, optimizing tension distribution across multiple vectors. Once adaptation was confirmed, the secondary defect was closed using single interrupted sutures (Figure 4), ensuring stable closure and optimal perfusion. The following postoperative days were uneventful, with no reported complications.

Figure 4: Intraoperative View: the Secondary Defect is Closed Using Single Interrupted Sutures

Discussion

The choice of reconstructive technique must consider several critical aspects: the extent and location of the defect, the presence of exposed structures, comorbidities and tissue mobility [4]. Whenever feasible, a less invasive approach is preferred, particularly in regions with limited skin mobility or tension distribution across multiple vectors - such as the back [4].

The double opposing rotational (Ying-Yang) flap represents a versatile reconstructive option. Although classically employed in scalp reconstruction [5], its application can be safely extended to other anatomical

regions, providing excellent functional preservation, reduced operative time, and minimal postoperative complications [6]. Modifications to this technique can further enhance functional outcomes and reduce postoperative complications.

In our clinical experience, the Ying-Yang reconstructive technique remains a safe and reliable option for defects of various sizes, even when applied to less conventional anatomical structures - such as the back region. However, as demonstrated in this case, innovative intraoperative modifications are often required to optimize outcomes. The additional incision employed in our case effectively redistributed the flap tension, while also minimizing the risk of postoperative complications, such as wound dehiscence or flap necrosis.

Conclusion

This case reinforces the importance of adaptive surgical thinking - integrating both geometrical precision with functional design - to personalized reconstruction based on each patient's anatomical and biomechanical requirements. While modifications can transform classical methods into more efficient and tailored solutions, surgeons should remain vigilant of potential postoperative complications, such as improper wound healing and wound dehiscence or partial flap necrosis, particularly in areas of limited vascularity or insufficient undermining.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Ethical Approval

Ethics approval statement is not required.

Informed Consent

Written informed consent for publication of their details was obtained from the patient.

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